

The residual growth landscape

A 43-model survey of residual stream dynamics and a post-hoc intervention study

Abstract

We measure the residual stream growth factor, the ratio of the last-layer residual norm to the first-layer norm, across 43 openly available language models spanning 18 architecture families and 70M to 4B parameters. Residual growth varies by over 500x across models (from 5x in OLMo-2 to 2,747x in Qwen3-1.7B) and shows no correlation with parameter count (Spearman $r = 0.043$, $p = 0.78$). Absolute RG values depend on calibration data (up to 1.9x variation), but rank ordering is stable (Spearman $r = 0.952$ across calibration conditions). We conduct two intervention studies on 9-10 models. First, Norm Equalization (NormEq), an analytical rescaling that forces uniform residual growth, degrades perplexity in 8 of 9 cases (one negligibly), with catastrophic failure (+2,073% PPL) in Qwen3-0.6B. Second, progressive layer dropping reveals that resilience to depth reduction is uncorrelated with residual growth ($r = -0.09$, $p = 0.80$): Falcon-H1 (RG = 9x) is the most fragile model, while GPT2-XL (RG = 510x) degrades gracefully. We conclude that heterogeneous residual growth is a learned feature of Pre-LN Transformer training, not an architectural defect, and that layer-level criticality depends on architecture type (SSM-hybrid layers are individually non-redundant) rather than residual dynamics.

1. Introduction

Pre-Layer Normalization (Pre-LN) has become the dominant Transformer configuration since its adoption in GPT-2 and subsequent scaling studies. A known consequence of Pre-LN is that residual stream norms grow monotonically through the network: each layer adds its output to an accumulating residual, and unlike Post-LN, there is no normalization applied after the addition. Prior work (Xiong et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022) has noted this growth pattern and proposed alternatives such as DeepNorm, but no study has systematically measured the magnitude and variation of residual growth across a broad sample of production models.

This work originated from a practical observation. When fine-tuning the later layers of Qwen3, the intervention produced clear improvements; the same procedure applied to Qwen3.5, however, had little effect. Investigating the cause, we measured the residual stream norms of both models and found that Qwen3's residual grows by roughly 2,700x from the first to the last layer, while Qwen3.5's grows by only ~48x. This 57-fold difference in a single architectural generation prompted a broader question: how much variation in residual growth exists across the open model ecosystem, and does it matter for model behavior?

This report presents three complementary studies. First, a survey of 43 models measuring residual growth factor, gradient coefficient of variation (GradCV), activation-gradient correlation, and layer pruning sensitivity. Second, an intervention experiment applying analytical residual rescaling (NormEq) to 9 models. Third, a layer dropping experiment testing whether models with different residual growth profiles show different robustness to depth reduction.

2. Methodology

2.1 Survey protocol

For each model, we compute four quantities using 20 calibration sentences covering factual, scientific, and technical domains. **Residual growth factor (RG)**: ratio of the L2 norm of the hidden state entering the last layer to that entering the first layer, averaged over all calibration tokens. **Gradient CV**: coefficient of variation of per-layer median gradient norms across all MLP projections. **Activation-gradient correlation**: Spearman rank correlation between per-layer activation magnitudes and gradient norms. **Layer pruning impact**: perplexity change when zeroing each layer's MLP output.

2.2 NormEq intervention

NormEq is an analytical (non-optimized) rescaling method. For each MLP layer, we compute a scalar alpha that would equalize the per-layer residual norm growth rate. Specifically, if the overall growth from layer 0 to layer N is G, the ideal per-layer growth rate is $g = G^{1/N}$. For each layer i, $\alpha_i = g / (\text{actual_step}_i)$, clipped to [0.1, 3.0]. Because NormEq involves no optimization, overfitting to calibration data is impossible by construction. We measure PPL on WikiText-2 train (calibration) and test (evaluation) splits with 256-token chunks.

2.3 Follow-up experiments

We extend both interventions along three axes. For layer dropping, we test four drop modes: **last-k** (remove deepest layers), **middle-k** (remove central layers), **even-k** (remove evenly spaced layers including first and last), and **random-k** (3 random seeds, averaged). For NormEq rescaling, we separately rescale **MLP-only**, **attention-only**, and **both** branches to isolate which component drives the degradation. All experiments are evaluated on three datasets: WikiText-2, AG News, and LAMBADA. Drop fractions are 10%, 20%, and 30%.

3. Survey results

3.1 The residual growth landscape

Figure 1. Residual growth factor (log scale) across 43 models, sorted by magnitude. Colors indicate architecture family. The range spans three orders of magnitude.

Residual growth varies from 5x (OLMo-2-0425-1B) to 2,747x (Qwen3-1.7B-Base), a factor of 550 between extremes. The median is 134x. Notable patterns emerge by architecture family: Qwen3 models occupy three of the top five positions, while all three Bloom models, all three Falcon-H1 models, and both OLMo models cluster in the bottom quintile.

3.2 No correlation with model size

Figure 2. Residual growth vs. parameter count, colored by family. Connected points show models within the same family at different sizes. Spearman $r = 0.043$ ($p = 0.78$).

Residual growth shows no statistically significant correlation with parameter count. SmoLLM2-135M (0.13B parameters) achieves 400x growth, while Bloom-3B (3.0B) shows only 7x. Within families, scaling behavior is inconsistent: Qwen2.5 grows monotonically with size (176x at 0.5B to 452x at 3B), while Qwen3 peaks at 1.7B (2,747x) and decreases at 4B (924x). This supports the view that residual growth is shaped primarily by architectural design choices (normalization placement, MLP structure, attention mechanism) rather than model scale.

3.3 Generational shift in Qwen

Figure 3. Qwen series comparison across three generations at matched sizes. Left: residual growth (log scale). Right: baseline perplexity (inverted: lower = better).

The Qwen lineage shows a marked shift across generations. Qwen3 amplified residual growth to extreme levels (2,747x at 1.7B), with only marginal PPL improvement over Qwen2.5 (12.9 vs 13.5). Qwen3.5, which adopts a Gated DeltaNet + Attention hybrid architecture, collapsed residual growth to 48x at 2B, a 57x reduction from Qwen3, while simultaneously achieving the best PPL in the family (10.8). This pattern is consistent with a deliberate architectural redesign that targets residual growth control while improving language modeling performance.

3.4 Cross-model correlations

Metric pair	Spearman r	p-value	Interpretation
RG vs GradCV	0.065	0.678	No relationship
RG vs Parameters	0.043	0.784	No relationship
RG vs PPL	-0.210	0.177	Weak (not significant)
GradCV vs PPL	0.314	0.040	Moderate positive

Table 1. Key cross-model correlations from the 43-model survey.

The most striking finding is the near-zero correlation between residual growth and gradient CV ($r = 0.065$). This means that models with wildly different residual dynamics can have similar gradient stability, implying that Pre-LN normalization successfully decouples forward-pass signal growth from backward-pass gradient flow. The only significant correlation is between GradCV and PPL ($r = 0.314$, $p = 0.04$),

suggesting that gradient uniformity, not residual uniformity, matters for model quality.

3.5 Calibration dependence of residual growth

Residual growth measurements differ depending on the calibration data used. The survey (Section 3.1-3.4) uses 20 short domain-diverse sentences, while the intervention experiments (Section 4) use WikiText-2 256-token chunks. For the 10 models measured under both conditions, absolute RG values can differ substantially: SmoLM2-1.7B measures 929x on the survey calibration but 495x on WikiText-2, and GPT2-XL measures 321x vs 571x (the only rank reversal). However, the rank order is highly stable (Spearman $r = 0.952$, Pearson $r = 0.991$ on log-scale). High-RG models remain high-RG, and low-RG models remain low-RG, regardless of calibration data.

Model	RG (survey)	RG (WikiText-2)	Ratio
Qwen3-1.7B-Base	2747x	2291x	1.20x
Qwen3-0.6B-Base	1232x	732x	1.68x
gemma-3-1b-pt	973x	860x	1.13x
SmoLM2-1.7B	929x	495x	1.88x
Qwen2.5-3B	452x	438x	1.03x
gpt2-xl	321x	571x	0.56x
pythia-2.8b	219x	232x	0.94x
Falcon-H1-1.5B-Base	9x	9x	1.03x
bloom-1b1	6x	7x	0.96x
OLMo-2-0425-1B	5x	6x	0.83x

Table 2. Residual growth under two calibration conditions. Survey uses 20 domain-diverse sentences; WikiText-2 uses 256-token chunks. Rank correlation $r = 0.952$ ($p < 0.0001$). Intervention sections (4.x) report WikiText-2 RG values; survey sections (3.x) report survey RG values.

4. Intervention experiments

Figure 4. Left: PPL change after NormEq rescaling (bars capped at 300% for readability; actual values annotated). Right: per-layer alpha profiles for selected models, showing the "kill zone" in early layers where alpha drops to 0.1.

Model	RG	Base PPL	NormEq PPL	Change	Alpha range
Qwen3-1.7B-Base	2291x	11.40	14.66	+28.6%	0.11 - 1.26
gemma-3-1b-pt	860x	50.72	50.60	-0.2%	0.12 - 1.29
Qwen3-0.6B-Base	732x	16.00	347.68	+2072.8%	0.13 - 1.23
gpt2-xl	571x	21.02	21.67	+3.1%	0.10 - 1.10
SmolLM2-1.7B	495x	10.76	36.43	+238.4%	0.19 - 1.26
Qwen2.5-3B	438x	10.04	10.49	+4.4%	0.10 - 1.18
pythia-2.8b	232x	14.13	16.53	+16.9%	0.10 - 1.31
Falcon-H1-1.5B-Base	9x	9.69	9.87	+1.9%	0.88 - 1.17
OLMo-2-0425-1B	6x	11.52	11.52	+0.0%	0.85 - 1.10

Table 3. NormEq intervention results across 9 models ordered by residual growth.

4.1 NormEq harms most models

NormEq degrades perplexity in 8 of 9 models tested. The sole exception is Gemma-3-1b-pt, which shows a negligible -0.2% change. Damage severity does not correlate linearly with residual growth: Qwen3-0.6B (RG = 732x) suffers catastrophic degradation (+2,073%), while Qwen3-1.7B (RG = 2,291x) degrades by only +29%. This suggests that the sensitivity to rescaling depends on how the model has distributed information across layers, not merely on how much the residual has grown.

4.2 The Layer 1 kill zone

Every high-RG model produces an alpha value of 0.10-0.19 at Layer 1, meaning NormEq must suppress the first MLP's contribution by 80-90% to equalize the residual growth profile. This is catastrophic because the early layers of Pre-LN Transformers perform fundamental feature extraction: token identity, positional

encoding integration, and basic syntactic patterns. Scaling these outputs to 10-13% of their original magnitude severely disrupts the model's perceptual foundation.

In contrast, low-RG models (Falcon-H1, OLMo-2) have relatively uniform alpha profiles (0.85-1.17), indicating their residual growth is already nearly equalized. NormEq has minimal effect on these models because there is little to correct.

4.3 The Gemma-3 anomaly

Gemma-3-1b-pt presents a puzzle: RG = 860x (top 5 in the survey), yet NormEq causes effectively zero damage (-0.2%). Its alpha profile shows the same Layer 1 drop (alpha = 0.12) as other high-RG models, yet the model is robust to this suppression. Combined with the layer dropping saturation (Section 4.4, where 50% depth reduction causes only 17x PPL increase), a consistent picture emerges: Gemma-3 appears to distribute its computation with unusual redundancy, concentrating critical information processing in its early layers while tolerating aggressive modification of the rest. (Anecdotally, we have also observed that Gemma-3 still produces coherent text after 90% unstructured weight pruning, though with substantial quality loss — a level of compression where most comparable models collapse entirely.) This may reflect Gemma's Peri-LN architecture (pre- and post-normalization around each sublayer). Understanding the architectural basis for this robustness is a valuable direction for compression research.

4.4 Layer dropping: which models tolerate depth reduction?

We test a complementary intervention: rather than rescaling layer outputs, we skip entire layers by replacing each dropped layer's output with its input (identity bypass). We progressively drop the last 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% of layers and measure PPL degradation on WikiText-2 test.

Figure 5. Left: PPL multiplier (log scale) when dropping the last N% of layers. Graceful degraders (GPT2-XL, Pythia-2.8b) stay below 10x at 20% drop; catastrophic degraders (Falcon-H1, Qwen2.5-3B) exceed 100x even at 10%. Right: PPL increase at 10% drop vs. residual growth, showing no systematic relationship.

Model	RG	Layers	Base PPL	D10%	D20%	D50%	Pattern
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Qwen3-1.7B-Base	2205x	28	11.4	5.7x	102.0x	5Kx	Moderate
gemma-3-1b-pt	862x	26	50.7	4.0x	11.0x	17.0x	Graceful
Qwen3-0.6B-Base	734x	28	16.0	3.2x	20.2x	1Kx	Graceful
gpt2-xl	510x	48	21.0	2.2x	5.9x	29.8x	Graceful
SmolLM2-1.7B	502x	24	10.8	64.3x	3Kx	58Bx	Moderate
Qwen2.5-3B	412x	36	10.0	211.9x	17Kx	640Kx	Catastrophic
pythia-2.8b	226x	32	14.1	3.2x	4.5x	179.9x	Graceful
Falcon-H1-1.5B-Base	9x	24	9.7	3Kx	354Kx	19Mx	Catastrophic
bloom-1b1	7x	24	25.5	2.3x	16.7x	3Kx	Graceful
OLMo-2-0425-1B	6x	16	11.5	5.2x	279.1x	71Kx	Moderate

Table 4. Layer dropping results. D10/20/50% show PPL multiplier vs baseline. "Graceful" = less than 5x at 10% drop; "Catastrophic" = over 100x.

4.5 Hypothesis rejected: resilience is not predicted by residual growth

The original hypothesis was that high-RG models, whose deep layers are "drowning" in a massive residual signal, would be more tolerant to layer removal. The data do not support this hypothesis: Spearman $r = -0.091$ ($p = 0.80$) between RG and 10%-drop PPL increase. Three distinct behavioral classes emerge instead.

Graceful degraders (GPT2-XL, Pythia-2.8b, Bloom-1b1, Qwen3-0.6B, Gemma-3): PPL increases by only 2-5x when 10% of layers are dropped. These models tend to have classic Pre-LN architecture or relatively deep layer stacks. Their deep layers contribute incrementally, making each individually expendable. Gemma-3 is additionally notable for saturating: dropping 50% of layers only increases PPL by 17x, suggesting that its critical computation is concentrated in the first half of the network.

Moderate degraders (Qwen3-1.7B, SmolLM2, OLMo-2): PPL increases 5-64x at 10% drop. SmolLM2 degrades steeply beyond 10%: while its initial 64x increase is moderate, it explodes to 3,000x at 20% and reaches billions at 30%, indicating high sensitivity in later layers despite a moderate initial response.

Catastrophic degraders (Falcon-H1, Qwen2.5-3B): PPL explodes even at 10% drop. Falcon-H1 is the most extreme case: removing just 2 of 24 layers increases PPL by 3,262x, despite having the lowest residual growth (RG = 9x) in the sample. This is consistent with SSM-Attention hybrid layers being individually non-redundant: unlike standard Transformer layers that add incremental refinement, each Mamba-based layer may perform a distinct state transition that cannot be skipped.

4.6 Drop position matters more than amount: the middle-layer finding

The follow-up experiments reveal that **where** layers are dropped matters far more than how many. Across all 8 models tested, dropping middle layers (center of the network) causes dramatically less damage than dropping the same number from the end. At 10% drop on WikiText-2, middle-drop increases PPL by only 18-77% across all models, while last-drop increases PPL by 182% to 434,052%. The last/middle damage ratio ranges from 5.6x (Pythia-2.8b) to 20,838x (Falcon-H1).

Evenly-spaced dropping is universally catastrophic, often worse than last-drop, because it removes layer 0 (the critical first layer). Random dropping produces intermediate results. This pattern is consistent across

WikiText-2, LAMBADA, and AG News, confirming that computation in Transformer-based LMs is concentrated at the network boundaries (first and last layers), with middle layers contributing incrementally.

Model	RG	Last 10%	Middle 10%	Last/Mid ratio
Qwen3-1.7B-Base	2291x	+1779%	+23%	78x
gemma-3-1b-pt	860x	+382%	+40%	10x
Qwen3-0.6B-Base	732x	+494%	+21%	24x
gpt2-xl	571x	+182%	+18%	10x
SmolLM2-1.7B	495x	+7178%	+19%	371x
pythia-2.8b	232x	+204%	+37%	6x
Falcon-H1-1.5B-Base	9x	+434052%	+21%	20838x
OLMo-2-0425-1B	6x	+3856%	+77%	50x

Table 5. Drop position comparison at 10% on WikiText-2. Middle layers are 6-20,800x more expendable than last layers.

4.7 MLP carries the residual growth signal, not Attention

Branch-decomposed NormEq reveals that **residual growth is predominantly an MLP phenomenon**. Rescaling attention outputs alone causes mild degradation (mean +15.6% PPL across all models), while rescaling MLP outputs alone causes severe degradation (mean +266%). Rescaling both branches simultaneously often compounds the damage superlinearly.

This makes mechanistic sense: in Pre-LN Transformers, the MLP sublayer is the primary contributor to the residual stream's magnitude growth. Attention redistributes information across positions but does not systematically increase the norm, whereas each MLP's SwiGLU/GELU activation can amplify the signal. Gemma-3 is again anomalous: both MLP-only and Attention-only rescaling produce near-zero impact (-0.1% and -0.0%), consistent with its earlier robustness to full NormEq.

Model	RG	MLP only	Attn only	Both
Qwen3-1.7B-Base	2291x	+29.1%	+14.0%	+59.1%
gemma-3-1b-pt	860x	-0.1%	-0.0%	-0.1%
Qwen3-0.6B-Base	732x	+1787.8%	+16.8%	+354657.5%
gpt2-xl	571x	+3.1%	+1.3%	+4.3%
SmolLM2-1.7B	495x	+291.9%	+32.0%	+18536.3%
pythia-2.8b	232x	+17.4%	+60.5%	+108.4%
Falcon-H1-1.5B-Base	9x	+2.0%	+0.1%	+1.9%
OLMo-2-0425-1B	6x	+0.0%	+0.0%	+0.0%

Table 6. Branch-decomposed NormEq on WikiText-2 eval. MLP rescaling is 17x more damaging on average than Attention rescaling.

5. Discussion

Figure 6. Study flow: observation across 43 models leads to targeted interventions, yielding the conclusion that residual growth is a learned feature.

5.1 Residual growth as learned feature

The two intervention studies converge on the same conclusion from different angles. NormEq shows that equalizing residual growth post-hoc destroys performance, meaning the heterogeneous growth profile encodes useful information. Layer dropping shows that models with extreme residual growth are not meaningfully more or less robust to depth reduction than low-growth models, meaning the growth factor does not indicate redundancy or inefficiency in deep layers.

This interpretation is consistent with the finding that residual growth and gradient CV are uncorrelated: the gradient flow (which drives learning) operates independently of the forward signal magnitude, thanks to Pre-LN's normalization before each sublayer. The model learns to exploit the growing residual as an information channel, even though (or because) it deviates from uniformity.

5.2 Three classes of layer criticality

The layer dropping experiment reveals a taxonomy that cross-cuts residual growth. **Graceful degraders** (GPT2-XL, Pythia, Bloom, Gemma-3) have layers that each contribute incrementally, making individual layers expendable. **Catastrophic degraders** (Falcon-H1, Qwen2.5-3B) have layers that are individually indispensable. Falcon-H1 is the most extreme example: despite having the lowest residual growth in the sample (RG = 9x), it is by far the most fragile to layer dropping. Each Mamba-based SSM layer performs a distinct state transition that cannot be bypassed, unlike Transformer layers that add incremental refinements to a shared residual representation.

Gemma-3 presents yet another anomaly: its PPL multiplier saturates at around 17x when dropping 50% of layers, actually declining from the 30% drop level. This suggests that Gemma-3 concentrates its critical computation in the first half of the network, with later layers providing diminishing and partially redundant contributions.

5.3 Design-time vs post-hoc control

The contrast between Qwen3 and Qwen3.5 provides a useful comparison. Under Qwen3's architecture, residual growth reached extreme levels (2,747x) with only modest PPL gains. Qwen3.5's shift to a Gated DeltaNet + Attention hybrid architecture coincides with 57x lower residual growth and better PPL. Similarly,

Falcon-H1's SSM-Attention hybrid maintains RG around 8-10x across all model sizes, consistent with SSM state transitions naturally constraining residual accumulation.

These patterns suggest that residual growth control may be most effective when built into the architecture, not applied as a post-hoc correction. This has direct implications for model compression: quantization and pruning methods that assume or require uniform signal magnitudes across layers may fail disproportionately on high-RG models.

5.4 Implications for compression and deployment

Models with extreme residual growth (Qwen3, SmoLM2) present challenges for post-training quantization. When the last-layer residual norm is 1,000-4,000x larger than the first-layer norm, a uniform quantization scheme must accommodate a much wider dynamic range, potentially sacrificing precision in early layers where absolute values are small but functionally critical. Layer-adaptive quantization strategies that account for per-layer residual magnitude may prove more effective for these models. Gemma-3 is an instructive exception: despite having $RG = 860x$, it tolerates NormEq and layer dropping with minimal degradation. This suggests that high residual growth alone does not preclude aggressive compression — the interaction with normalization architecture (Peri-LN in Gemma-3's case) may matter more than the growth factor itself. The layer dropping results add a further dimension: layer pruning strategies that assume deep layers are safe to remove will fail catastrophically on SSM-hybrid architectures like Falcon-H1, where every layer is individually critical. Conversely, deep Pre-LN Transformer stacks (GPT2-XL, Pythia) are amenable to 10-20% depth reduction with modest PPL cost, making them better candidates for layer-removal compression.

6. Limitations

This study is limited in several ways. All models are 4B parameters or smaller due to GPU memory constraints; residual growth behavior at larger scales remains unexplored. The calibration set is small (20 sentences for the survey, 96-150 chunks for interventions) and predominantly English. As shown in Section 3.5, absolute residual growth values are sensitive to calibration data (up to 1.9x variation between our two conditions), though rank ordering is highly stable ($r = 0.952$); future work should establish standardized measurement protocols. The initial NormEq experiments applied rescaling only to MLP outputs; follow-up branch-decomposed experiments additionally tested attention-only and both-branch rescaling, confirming MLP as the primary locus of sensitivity, but the decomposition was limited to 8 models and 3 datasets. We measure only the residual stream L2 norm and do not analyze directional properties (e.g., whether growth is isotropic or concentrated along specific subspaces). The layer dropping experiments use simple identity bypass rather than more sophisticated skip connections. Finally, we test only analytical rescaling; other approaches such as layer-wise learning rate adjustment or targeted fine-tuning after rescaling are left for future work.

7. Key findings

- **500x variation.** Residual growth spans 5x to 2,747x across 43 models with no correlation to model size, supporting the view that this is a design-level property.

- **Generational reversal.** Qwen3 pushed residual growth to extremes; Qwen3.5 reversed course with a hybrid architecture, achieving better PPL at 57x lower growth.
- **Hybrid SSMs constrain growth.** Falcon-H1 maintains RG ~ 8-10x regardless of model size, suggesting SSM state transitions naturally limit residual accumulation.
- **Forward-backward decoupling.** Residual growth and gradient CV are uncorrelated ($r = 0.065$), meaning Pre-LN successfully isolates gradient flow from forward signal growth.
- **Post-hoc rescaling fails.** NormEq degrades 8/9 models, with catastrophic failure in some cases. Early layers (L1-L3) are the most sensitive.
- **Layer dropping is uncorrelated with RG.** Falcon-H1 (RG = 9x) is the most fragile to layer removal, while GPT2-XL (RG = 510x) degrades gracefully. Architecture type, not residual dynamics, determines layer criticality.
- **SSM layers appear non-redundant.** Unlike Transformer layers that contribute incrementally, each Mamba-based layer in Falcon-H1 appears to perform a distinct state transition that cannot be bypassed.
- **Middle layers are universally expendable.** Dropping middle layers causes 6-20,800x less damage than dropping the same number of last layers, across all models and datasets.
- **MLP is the residual growth culprit.** Branch-decomposed NormEq shows that rescaling MLP outputs is 17x more damaging than rescaling Attention outputs. Residual growth is an MLP phenomenon.
- **Residual growth is learned.** The convergent evidence from NormEq and layer dropping shows that heterogeneous growth profiles are a feature of training, not a defect.

Data and code. The complete measurement data (JSON) and experiment scripts are available alongside this report. All models were accessed via HuggingFace Hub and measured on a single L4 GPU. Total compute: approximately 5 GPU-hours for the survey and 5 GPU-hours for the intervention study.

Appendix A: Full 43-model survey data

Complete measurements for all 43 models, sorted by residual growth factor (descending). RG = residual growth, GCV = gradient coefficient of variation, GR = gradient ratio (max/min), AvG = activation-gradient Spearman r, PvG = pruning-gradient Spearman r, PvA = pruning-activation Spearman r.

Model	Params	L	RG	GCV	GR	AvG	PvG	PvA	PPL
Qwen3-1.7B-Base	1.72B	28	2747x	0.272	3.0x	-0.61	+0.28	+0.18	12.9
Qwen3-0.6B-Base	0.60B	28	1232x	0.265	2.7x	-0.47	+0.36	+0.34	15.1
gemma-3-1b-pt	1.00B	26	973x	0.306	3.4x	-0.68	-0.07	+0.49	32.6
SmolLM2-1.7B	1.71B	24	929x	0.331	3.0x	+0.01	+0.82	+0.03	17.4
Qwen3-4B-Base	4.02B	36	924x	0.289	75.9x	-0.52	-0.25	+0.29	12.8
SmolLM2-360M	0.36B	32	832x	0.278	2.9x	+0.27	+0.83	+0.35	17.8
Qwen2.5-3B	3.09B	36	452x	0.389	432.1x	-0.38	+0.04	+0.35	11.2
stablelm-2-1_6b	1.64B	24	402x	0.089	1.6x	+0.52	+0.22	+0.04	23.6
SmolLM2-135M	0.13B	30	400x	0.557	5.5x	-0.03	+0.81	+0.15	28.9
gpt2-xl	1.56B	48	321x	0.216	2.1x	+0.05	+0.04	+0.15	26.4
RedPajama-INCITE-Base-3B-v1	2.78B	32	318x	0.195	2.2x	+0.57	+0.46	+0.72	20.6
Qwen2.5-1.5B	1.54B	28	308x	0.137	1.6x	-0.18	-0.13	+0.65	13.5
pythia-1.4b	1.41B	24	261x	0.181	2.0x	+0.13	+0.61	+0.38	23.4
pythia-1b	1.01B	16	243x	0.152	1.7x	-0.10	+0.18	+0.78	25.0
gpt2-medium	0.35B	24	226x	0.431	4.1x	-0.23	-0.12	+0.56	43.9
pythia-2.8b	2.78B	32	219x	0.144	1.7x	+0.40	-0.03	+0.40	21.6
Falcon3-1B-Base	1.67B	18	211x	0.195	2.0x	+0.69	+0.02	+0.13	16.1
Qwen2.5-0.5B	0.49B	24	176x	0.127	1.6x	+0.39	+0.74	+0.46	15.4
phi-1	1.42B	24	162x	0.192	2.0x	-0.57	+0.54	-0.18	104.1
phi-1_5	1.42B	24	160x	0.050	1.4x	-0.12	-0.05	+0.19	11.8
gpt2-large	0.77B	36	134x	0.226	2.2x	+0.49	+0.01	+0.58	31.4
Cerebras-GPT-1.3B	1.32B	24	134x	0.445	3.7x	-0.70	+0.66	-0.51	42.9
phi-2	2.78B	32	131x	0.220	2.6x	-0.35	-0.37	+0.58	11.0
pythia-410m	0.41B	24	110x	0.130	1.6x	-0.14	+0.37	+0.53	38.5
open_llama_3b_v2	3.43B	26	110x	0.175	4.5x	+0.63	+0.37	+0.16	20.8
gpt2	0.12B	12	87x	0.558	4.6x	-0.64	-0.18	+0.66	75.3
Llama-3.2-3B	3.21B	28	81x	0.104	1.4x	+0.38	-0.17	+0.02	19.0
TinyLlama-1.1B-intermediate-step-1431k-1.1B	1.1B	22	76x	0.128	1.6x	-0.18	+0.61	-0.27	33.4
pythia-160m	0.16B	12	68x	0.625	12.5x	-0.17	+0.29	+0.75	122.3
Llama-3.2-1B	1.24B	16	56x	0.078	1.3x	+0.03	+0.30	+0.04	22.0
Qwen3.5-2B-Base	1.88B	24	48x	0.221	2.0x	-0.57	-0.43	+0.59	10.8
pythia-70m	0.07B	6	42x	0.795	42.2x	-0.37	+0.77	+0.09	854.1
OLMo-1B-hf	1.18B	16	16x	0.105	1.4x	+0.69	+0.67	+0.51	26.7
Qwen3.5-0.8B-Base	0.75B	24	15x	0.221	2.0x	-0.35	-0.05	+0.64	13.0
deepseek-coder-1.3b-base	1.35B	24	13x	0.474	3.4x	-0.41	+0.73	-0.18	133.6
bloom-560m	0.56B	24	12x	0.308	24.5x	+0.28	+0.45	+0.41	60.1

Model	Params	L	RG	GCV	GR	AvG	PvG	PvA	PPL
Falcon-H1-0.5B-Base	0.52B	36	10x	0.192	1.9x	+0.55	+0.64	+0.53	12.6
Falcon-H1-1.5B-Base	1.55B	24	9x	0.200	2.1x	+0.52	+0.52	+0.72	15.2
gemma-2-2b	2.61B	26	8x	0.245	2.4x	-0.73	+0.56	-0.22	34.0
Falcon-H1-3B-Base	3.15B	32	8x	0.167	2.1x	+0.21	+0.45	+0.77	13.5
bloom-3b	3.00B	30	7x	0.375	10.2x	+0.42	-0.07	+0.40	28.5
bloom-1b1	1.07B	24	6x	0.168	2.1x	+0.49	+0.09	+0.46	35.9
OLMo-2-0425-1B	1.48B	16	5x	0.274	2.4x	+0.81	-0.02	+0.05	16.8

Table A1. Full survey results. Red-highlighted cells indicate top-5 residual growth; green-highlighted cells indicate bottom-5.

Appendix B: Architecture classification

Family	n	RG range	Norm type	Key features
Qwen3	3	924-2,747x	Pre-LN (RMS)	RoPE, GQA, SwiGLU
Qwen2.5	3	176-452x	Pre-LN (RMS)	RoPE, GQA, SwiGLU
Qwen3.5	2	15-48x	Pre-LN (RMS)	Gated DeltaNet + Attn hybrid
Gemma-3	1	973x	Peri-LN (RMS)	RoPE, GQA, pre+post norm
Gemma-2	1	8x	Pre+Post-LN	Logit soft-capping
SmolLM2	3	400-929x	Pre-LN (RMS)	Llama-based, small scale
Falcon-H1	3	8-10x	Pre-LN	SSM (Mamba2) + Attention hybrid
Falcon3	1	211x	Pre-LN	Pruned+distilled from 7B
Llama-family	4	56-110x	Pre-LN (RMS)	Llama-3.2, TinyLlama, OpenLlama
Pythia	6	42-261x	Pre-LN (LN)	GPT-NeoX arch, rotary
GPT-2	4	87-321x	Pre-LN (LN)	Classic Pre-LN Transformer
Bloom	3	6-12x	Pre-LN (LN)	ALiBi, embedding LN, GeLU
Phi	3	131-162x	Pre-LN (LN)	Textbook-quality data
OLMo	2	5-16x	Peri-LN (RMS)	OLMo-1: Pre-LN; OLMo-2: reordered norm
StableLM	1	402x	Pre-LN (LN)	LLaMA-like, RoPE, SwiGLU
Cerebras	1	134x	Pre-LN (LN)	GPT-2 architecture variant
RedPajama	1	318x	Pre-LN (RMS)	Llama-based, open data
DeepSeek	1	13x	Pre-LN (RMS)	Code-focused training

Table B1. Architecture classification of model families included in the survey. Norm type and key architectural features are based on published model cards and source code.

Data and code. The complete measurement data (JSON) and experiment scripts are available alongside this report. All models were accessed via HuggingFace Hub and measured on a single L4 GPU. Total compute: approximately 5 GPU-hours for the survey and 5 GPU-hours for the intervention study.